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CRITERIA FOR SELECTION OF EDUCATIONAL MATERIAL FOR THE FORMATION OF FUTURE PHILOLOGISTS' KOREAN LINGUISTIC AND SOCIO-CULTURAL COMPETENCE IN SPEAKING

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As we can see, the modern processes of modernization of higher education cause particular importance for the formation of professionally-oriented communicative socio-cultural competence, the primary task of the institution is the formation of professional and communicative competence. Korean language didactics needs research, developing and testing of the new teaching methods, because the Korean language is typologically different from the Ukrainian language, the culture of nonverbal behavior of Koreans has no analogues in the world. The study raises issues of modern methods of teaching foreign languages, focuses on the relationship between language and culture, based on the formation of socio-cultural competence.

The article is devoted to the definition of the main criteria, for which the selection of didactic material for the teaching of Korean oral students can be developed, as well as the formation of Korean linguistic and socio-cultural competence in speaking. The concept of Korean-speaking linguistic and socio-cultural competence in conversations with future philologists is determined, its role and place in the university curriculum are analyzed. The analysis of structural-component conformity of competence is carried out, special attention is paid to the main tasks and stages of formation of linguistic and sociocultural competence in accordance with the level of students' language proficiency. The definition of the concept of culturally marked vocabulary in the Korean language is proposed. The procedure for selecting educational material is outlined. The selection of educational lexical material for the formation of Korean linguistic and socio-cultural competence in speaking on the basis of qualitative and quantitative indicators is done. The selection and the analysis of culturally marked lexical items, culturally marked monologues-samples and dialogues-samples are carried out. Methodical recommendations for the formation of Korean linguistic and socio-cultural competence in speaking are also given

Keywords: *competence, linguistic and sociocultural competence, criteria for selection of educational material, Korean philologist*

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1. Introduction

The creation of multi-sectoral contacts between Korea and Ukraine over the past 30 years indicates the need for training highly qualified specialists in the field of Korean studies (philologists and translators) who are able to provide high-level communication that will serve various directions of bilateral relations.

Currently, ten institutions of higher education in Ukraine train Korean language specialists. And there are already significant developments in the theory and practice of its teaching. However, the available works are far from exhaustive of all the problems of Korean language teaching methodology. Currently, Korean language didactics needs thorough research, development and testing of new teaching methods, because the Korean language is typologically different from the Ukrainian and German languages (which students have studied since school), and the culture of non-verbal behavior of Koreans has practically no analogues in the world. This creates a

number of additional difficulties of a lingual, extralingual and paralingual nature in learning the Korean language, and also requires the search for new ways to optimize the learning process, the use of new information and educational resources.

2. Literary review

There are many developments in the theory and practice of teaching foreign languages. The subject of scientific research was modern approaches to teaching Oriental languages, the selection of Oriental lexical material [1], analysis of the shortcomings of the Korean language teaching methodology [2, 3]. The principles of learning foreign languages were repeatedly highlighted, the requirements for the educational process as a whole and its components (goals, knowledge, methods, learning process) were analyzed, the most relevant learning methods were chosen for the formation of linguistic and sociocultural competence in speaking [4]. Scientific

achievements in the field of linguistic and cultural studies have laid the foundations for the development of a linguistic and cultural paradigm in the teaching of foreign languages, when cultural phenomena are studied through the lens of language, mastering a language is possible only through understanding the culture of the people who speak the language, penetrating into their worldview, mentality, living environment, into the linguistic picture of the world. The formation of linguistic and sociocultural competence in future Korean philologists is carried out on the basis of linguistic and cultural studies. Linguistic culture is defined as a discipline that studies the manifestation, reflection and fixation of the culture of each nation in language and discourse, which is directly related to the study of the national picture of the world, language consciousness, and the peculiarities of the mental-linguistic complex [5]. The problems of the need for joint study of language and culture [6], analysis of country studies and cultural studies approaches as one of the main provisions of foreign language teaching methods remain relevant [7].

Taking into account the significant interest of the scientific community in the problems of language learning, we state that until now the issue of researching a comprehensive methodology for the formation of Korean linguistic and sociocultural competence in speaking in higher education has not been raised. In addition, the teaching of spoken Korean in Ukraine is still carried out without taking into account the conditions of a specific academic environment, without programmatic orderliness of courses, and is often the work of enthusiastic teachers. Therefore, there was a need to systematize the process of teaching oral Korean speech, as well as to introduce the method of formation of Korean linguistic and sociocultural competence in speaking into the educational process of higher education institutions.

3. Research aim and tasks

The aim of the study is to reveal the features of the criteria for selecting educational material for the formation of Korean-speaking linguistic, sociocultural competence in future philologists.

To achieve the goal, the following tasks are set:

1) to analyze criteria for the selection of educational material for the formation of Korean-speaking linguistic and sociocultural competence in future philologists;

2) to carry out a selection of educational material for the formation of Korean-speaking linguistic and sociocultural competence in future philologists.

4. Research materials and methods

The theoretical and methodological basis of this research was the use of theoretical methods: analysis and generalization of sources from pedagogy, linguistic didactics, linguistics in order to highlight the content of linguistic and sociocultural competence in speaking; linguistic, methodical principles of education, for the selection of linguistic and sociocultural material. In order to compare the existing scientific approaches to the interpretation of the concept of "linguistic-sociocultural competence", the method of comparison was used.

5. Research results

Learning a foreign language is possible only if you master the culture. Today, society faces the question of training the future philologist, who in his/her professional activity will have the ability and a sufficient level of knowledge to instantly respond to the various challenges of certain cultures in the conditions of intercultural relations and intercultural communication. It has already become axiomatic, that one of the leading goals of professional education today is the preparation of a qualified graduate who will not only have excellent knowledge of a foreign language, but will also be competent and competitive in the labor market. Society requires him/her to be mobile, always ready for self-development and improvement.

Since the 2000s, joint study of language and culture has been developing rapidly. The concepts of linguistic and cultural, sociocultural, sociolinguistic, linguistic and regional studies, intercultural, intercultural communicative, cultural and regional studies, cross-cultural competences are used. However, it is worth noting, that the concept of linguo-sociocultural competence (competency) is getting the most use. In the early 2000s, a linguistic-sociocultural approach, a linguistic-sociocultural method, culturally appropriate technologies, and an ethnocultural paradigm of foreign language learning were developed [8]. The co-study of language and culture is closely related to the study of foreign languages at all levels - from secondary school to higher education institutions, both in the process of training philologists and in the process of teaching foreign languages for special purposes. Using the language in the professional and everyday sphere with native speakers requires both the mastery of the actual speech skills – speaking, reading, writing and listening, as well as linguistic and sociocultural parameters – and the mastery of the language in its culture-bearing function. A professional language user must be familiar with the culture, everyday life, concepts and realities of the native people, possess culturally marked language units, non-verbal means of communication, verbal and non-verbal behavior. Possession of a language in a culture-bearing function makes it possible to establish and maintain any cooperation with foreigners [9].

In modern science, the linguistic and sociocultural component has occupied a dominant niche in the paradigm of foreign language learning. Studying communication as a type of activity, Edward Hall described the parameters of communicative differences, which were culturally determined [10], the problem of the development of linguistic sociocultural competence itself was considered by N. Andronkina, N. Borysko [11, 12].

Having analyzed the definition of linguistic and sociocultural competence, we came to the conclusion that the most complete is the definition, proposed by I. Bachynska: "a system of linguistic and extralinguistic knowledge (regional knowledge, norms of verbal and non-verbal behavior of native speakers depending on the conditions of social interaction), speech skills (operating with culturally marked language units) and ones (to understand/produce speech, to relate the same information to language units as native speakers; to observe the norms of verbal and non-verbal speech behavior

depending on the conditions of social interaction) that ensure the ability of an individual to engage in intercultural communication" [13]. This understanding of linguo-sociocultural competence covers its lingual and extra-lingual aspects, focuses on speech skills and abilities, integrates cultural and linguistic knowledge with speech skills.

A necessary condition for revealing the concept of linguistic sociocultural competence in future philologists of the Korean language is the selection of educational material [14]. The effectiveness of the formation of competence, the effectiveness of knowledge, skills and abilities depends on the correctness of the selected material, it optimizes the students' reflection of their own learning results, and activates the motivation to study. During the preparation of linguistic and sociocultural material, it is necessary to take into account the content of linguistic and sociocultural competence, the possibilities of information technologies, the age characteristics of the subjects of study, and the selection criteria.

In the selection of linguistic and sociocultural material, it is important to determine the units of selection. Based on the component composition of linguistic and sociocultural competence, as well as analyzing the works of scientists, devoted to linguistic and sociocultural material, we define the following positions:

- a culturally marked lexical unit (word, phraseology);
- a culturally marked non-verbal means of communication;
- a culturally marked monologue-sample (printed: description or story; as well as audio-video monologue: description or story);
- a culturally marked sample dialogue (printed dialogue, audio-video dialogue).

In determining the procedure for selecting educational material, we define the following operations:

- study of spheres, topics and situations of professional activity of future philologists, analysis of curricula for the 1st-2nd course in the practice of the Korean language, as well as in other languages that are taught at the initial stage; analysis of pan-European recommendations on language education (initial level A1–A2);
- selection of culturally marked lexical units;
- selection of non-verbal means of communication;
- creation of thematic lists of culturally marked words with their lexical meanings, phrases where the functional features of these words are represented;
- selection of informative texts (sample monologues) that contain extralingual information about the culture and daily life of Koreans;
- organization of educational and thematic complexes, which include culturally marked vocabulary, fragments of non-verbal behavior, sample dialogues and monologues, informative texts.

Selection of culturally marked lexical units. We define a culturally marked lexical unit as a unit (word, phraseology) that denotes a referent of Korean culture that is absent in Ukrainian, that has structural (composites and phraseology), semantic (differs in content, connotative meanings) and functional (has distinctive features of use) disagreements with a lexical unit of the native language with a common reference correlation

with Korean. Culturally marked vocabulary plays an extremely important role in the production and perception of speech when communicating with representatives of other cultures, because culture is woven into language to a greater or lesser extent even at the initial stage of learning - within such situations as acquaintance, family, clothes, meals, products, etc. The selection of lexical material is carried out according to criteria. By **the selection criteria**, we understand the main features, with the help of which educational material is qualitatively and quantitatively evaluated for the purpose of using it or not using it as educational material in accordance with the goals of education [14]. In determining the criteria for the selection of lexical material, we define a number of criteria that are relevant to the selection of linguistic-sociocultural vocabulary: i.e., the criterion of cultural markedness, the criterion of frequency and sufficient quantity, thematicity, semantic value, compatibility, adequacy of the lexical material for the purposes of learning. We define the criterion of etiquette as special for the selection of the Korean language vocabulary.

According to the criterion of cultural markedness, words, in which a cultural component can be traced in the structure of the word, the semantics of the word and the functional range are subject to selection, taking into account the peculiarities of the vocabulary of the Korean language, we define the following groups of culturally marked vocabulary that are subject to selection: completely non-equivalent vocabulary (김치 Kimchhi, 쪽 Chchuk, 젓물 – water mixed with ashes of burnt straw or wood, used for washing clothes); partially equivalent vocabulary (권 – a volume, a book, part of a book, non-equivalent meaning: a unit of account for one binding, which consisted of 20 pages); words that differ in the denotative semantic range 지키다 (to protect = to ward, to guard), 경호하다 (to protect = to provide one's safety), 두둔하다 (to protect = to stand up for someone, to provide support), 변호하다 (to protect = to defend someone, for example, in court), 어린이 (a child from 4–5 years old and before starting school); words that differ in the connotative semantic range 돼지 a pig, a domestic animal, figuratively – a bad, stupid and miserly person, 마음 heart, soul, character, feeling, mood, desire, sympathy, intention, aspiration); words that differ in structure 남자아이 (a boy, literally – a man-child); precedent words (한강 Han-gang river, 금강 Kungang river, 남산 Namsan mountain); phraseology (귀가 얇다 to have thin ears, to be gullible, 마음이 굴뚝같다 to burn with desire; words that differ in denotative and connotative meanings: yes, in the Ukrainian language, the hyperonym "animal" has the meaning: "any creature unlike a plant or a person", "rude, vile person"; hyponyms for this word are: beast "wild, usually predatory, animal", "fierce, cruel person"; livestock "individual four-legged domestic farm animal", "enslaved person", cattle "individual four-legged domestic farm animal", "vile, cruel person" [15] In the Korean language, there are many more words for "animal", the semantic range of which does not coincide with Ukrainian language: 동물 an animal, a living being that moves independently (except a human) 짐승 an ani-

mal, a beast, a living creature that has fur on its body and four legs (there is no special nomen in the Ukrainian language), a cruel or wild person; 애완동물 a pet (Ukrainian, it's also an animal); 내혈동물 a cold-blooded animal [16].

The frequency criterion is one of the most used criteria for the selection of lexical material. According to this selection criterion, the most frequently used words are subject to selection. However, it should be noted right away, that currently in Ukraine there is no dictionary of the frequency of the Korean language, according to which it would be possible to determine the frequency of use of this or that word and thus form a dictionary of culturally marked vocabulary. On the other hand, there are words that are not often used in everyday speech, but they should be studied, because knowledge of these words creates a coherent model of hypo-hyperonymic relations in the minds of students, and also enables the use of lexical units within the same thematic group.

The thematic criterion involves the selection and grouping of lexical units according to relevant topics. According to the curriculum, the following topics are studied in the 1–2 courses: "Acquaintance", "Family", "Clothing", "Food and drinks", "Products. Goods", "Trade and leisure facilities", "Housing and living conditions", "Sports and recreation", "Telephone conversation", "Holidays and significant dates", "Seasons. Weather. Climate", "Health care", "Infrastructure, means of transportation", "Hobbies", "Travel", "Food establishments", "Human appearance", "Education in Korea", "Emergencies", "Vegetables and fruits", "Flora and fauna of Korea", "Outstanding places of South Korea".

The criterion of semantic value. According to this criterion, such lexical units, in which the culturally marked component of semantics is fully or partially expressed - in denotative and/or connotative meanings, are to be selected. According to this criterion, lexical units should be selected that have partial non-equivalence, in which the range of denotative and connotative meanings does not coincide with the Ukrainian language.

Culturally marked vocabulary that corresponds to social contacts of real foreign language communication and typical situations of foreign language communication is subject to the criteria of adequacy of lexical material to the goals. Lexical knowledge and skills are implemented in speech skills, in particular in speaking skills. Accordingly, students should master such a vocabulary that will be sufficient for the production of dialogic and monologic speech at the A1–A2 levels (according to the subject of our research). To construct utterances, students must possess culturally marked words of all parts of speech, semantic and functional features of words.

The criterion of etiquette is aimed at the selection of linguistic means that are characteristic of the communication etiquette of Koreans, taking into account the status, age, and gender characteristics of the partners. In accordance with this selection criterion, lexical units – means of address – are subject to selection (너 – addressing to a friend or subordinate) 사모님 – to a woman who is the wife of a man whose social status is higher than the

speaker's one), honorific suffixes and honorific infixes (씨, 군, 여사, 시, 으시).

Selection of culturally marked sample monologues and sample dialogues

Culturally marked texts (dialogues and monologues) are considered texts that contain information about the culture of South Korea, culturally marked lexical units, elements of non-verbal behavior (audio-video dialogues), which have the following educational functions: they contain the necessary culturally marked extralingual information that students will be able to use during talking; audio-video dialogues contain elements of non-verbal behavior of Koreans; create an informational and linguistic basis for oral monologic and dialogic speech.

According to the criterion of saturation with country-scientific realities, the texts that contain information about the culture, daily life, and natural environment of Koreans; culturally marked units that denote cultural concepts and realities are subject to selection; such texts should contain a story or description of a cultural object, reveal its essence from different angles. Texts should serve as an information source for oral speech, demonstrate the peculiarities of using culturally marked vocabulary, so that students imitate the syntagmatic relations of lexical units in oral speech.

Texts that contain sufficient information about a certain cultural reality, but in such a volume that students can learn, are subject to the selection criterion of correspondence to the life and speech experience of students. In addition, students' speaking experience should be taken into account. As practice shows, during the first course (corresponding to the A1 level), students can read and listen to only separate supraphrase units (mini-texts). At the end of the second year (corresponding to the A2 level), students read and listen to texts of up to 200–250 words. Therefore, for the first course, you should select mini-texts that contain explicit elementary information about the culture and daily life of Koreans. For the second course, it is worth choosing texts, ranging from 100 to 200–250 words, which contain more complete information about the cultural environment of Koreans.

According to the criterion of correlation of information with the native language culture, the texts that contain information, contrasting with the Ukrainian language culture, are primarily subject to selection. In accordance with the purpose of the study, we will summarize the obtained results.

In the selection of texts for learning to speak Korean, we rely on the following aspects of authenticity:

1) cultural authenticity – the presence of information about the peculiarities of the life of native speakers, the natural environment of their existence in the texts;

2) informative authenticity – the presence of relevant information about the culture and daily life of modern Koreans in the texts,

3) situational authenticity – the presence (for example, in audio-video dialogue) of a natural situation of communication, as well as the creation of such a situation and communication within this situation,

4) the authenticity of the national mentality – the presence of culturally marked foreign language phrases,

5) reactive authenticity – the ability of the text to cause real emotional, mental and linguistic reactions. At the elementary level, students begin to read full-fledged texts only from the second year, in the first year we limit ourselves to only sentences and supraphrase units (mini-texts), which make up the selection units: a caption text that comments on the image of a certain cultural concept; text-commentary that interprets a certain cultural phenomenon of a plot nature; text-dialogue that contains authentic verbal means characteristic of a certain communicative situation.

All these texts are characterized by cultural, informative, situational national-mental authenticity. For second-year students, we select the following authentic texts: narrative texts and descriptive texts (longer, in 200–250 words), which accompany images of cultural realities, phenomena, etc.

The criterion of typological diversity involves the selection of sample texts (printed and audio-video dialogues) of various functional types, provided by the curriculum: monologue-narrative, monologue-description, dialogue-interrogation, dialogue-etiquette and dialogue-arrangement.

The criterion of the ratio of verbal and non-verbal components of dialogue. According to this criterion, we select only those audio-video dialogues that contain non-verbal components [17].

The criterion of situationality refers primarily to the selection of audio-video materials: those audio-video dialogues, in which the components of the communicative situation are realized as fully as possible, in particular, the following: status roles of the sender and the addressee, communicative purpose, code, style, ethnic environment, are considered good. It is these markers that make it possible to represent the linguistic and sociocultural component in both verbal and non-verbal means, and demonstrate the concepts of Korean communication.

The conducted research does not exhaust all the problems of selecting educational material for the formation of future Korean linguistic and sociocultural competence in speaking. As a perspective of further research, we define the formation of a subsystem of exercises for the formation of future Korean linguistic and sociocultural competence in speaking.

6. Conclusions

1. It was determined, that the criteria for the selection of culturally marked vocabulary are the criteria of cultural marking, frequency and sufficient quantity, thematicity, semantic value, compatibility, adequacy of the lexical material for the purposes of learning.

It was found, that the criteria for the selection of non-verbal means of communication are the criteria of cultural orientation, functionality, speech etiquette, and the status of communication partners.

It was proven, that the selection of sample monologues and sample dialogues should be carried out on the basis of the following criteria: saturation with country studies realities, culturally marked lexical units, thematic marking, correspondence to the life and speech experience of students, correlation of information with native linguistic culture, authenticity, criterion of audio text presentation quality, criterion of genre and typological diversity, criterion of ratio of verbal and non-verbal components of dialogue, criterion of situationality.

2. The selection of educational material was made for the formation of Korean linguistic and sociocultural competence in speaking in future philologists.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

References

1. Asadchykh, O. V. (2011). Suchasni pidkhody do navchannia skhidnomovnoho leksychnoho materialu. Naukovi zapysky Vinnytskoho derzhavnogo pedahohichnoho universytetu imeni Mykhaila Kotsiubynskoho. Seriya: Pedahohika i psykhohohika, 35, 56–60.
2. Voronina, L. A. (2016). Spetsifika metodiki obucheniia koreiskomu iazyku kak inostrannomu na nachalnom etape v vuze. Saint-Petersburg: Izd-vo RGPU im. A.I. Gercena, 127.
3. Yeong-ran, K. (2011). Korean language textbooks and research on Korean language teaching in the light of language teaching theory. Seoul, 277.
4. Azimov, E. G., Shchukin, A. N. (2009). Novyi slovar metodicheskikh terminov i poniatii (teoriia i praktika obucheniia iazykam). Moscow: IKAR, 446.
5. Zahnitko, A. P. (2017). Lihvokulturolohiiia. Vinnytsia, 287.
6. Mak, A. S., Westwood, M. J., Ishiyama, F. I., Barker, M. (2000). The sociocultural competencies for success among international students: The Excell Program. Journal of International Education, 4 (2), 33–38.
7. Safina, M. S. (2014). Formation of Socio-cultural Competence in Foreign Language Teaching. Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences, 136, 80–83. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.05.292>
8. Sem'ian, N. V. (2019). Formuvannia u maibutnikh filolohiv anhlomovnoi lihvosotsiokulturnoi kompetentnosti v chytanni zasobamy poetychnoho tvor. Kyiv, 234.
9. Wonjung, M. (2016). Implicit notions of identity: the absence of explicit communication in Korean hybrid greetings. Universitas, 31 (2), 119–140. doi: <http://doi.org/10.4067/s0718-23762016000200008>
10. Hall, E.T. (1976). Beyond Culture. New York: Anchor Press, 235.
11. Andronkina, N. M. (2009). Kognitivno-deiatel'nostnyi podkhod k formirovaniu lingvosotciokulturnoi kompetentcii v obuchenii nemetckomu iazyku studentov iazykovogo vuza. Ros.gos. ped. un-t im. A. I. Gercena. Saint-Petersburg, 49.
12. Borisko, N. F. (2000). Teoreticheskie osnovy sozdaniia uchebno-metodicheskikh kompleksov dlia iazykovoi mezhkulturnoi podgotovki uchitelei inostrannykh iazykov. Kyiv: Kievskii gos. lingvist. un-t., 300–308.
13. Bachinska, I. A. (2016). Formuvannia anglomovnoi lingvosotciokulturnoi kompetentcii uchniv starshoi shkoli. Kyiv, 23.

14. Hasanova, S. (2014). Linguo-Cultural Aspect of Interrelation of Language and Culture. *International Journal of English Linguistics*, 4 (6), 160–166. doi: <http://doi.org/10.5539/ijel.v4n6p160>
15. Akademichnyi tlumachnyi slovnyk ukrainskoi movy. Available at: <http://sum.in.ua/s/skot>
16. Russko-koreiskii slovar. Available at: <https://krdict.korean.go.kr/rus/dicSearch/search?nation=rus&nationCode=5&ParaWordNo=&mainSearchWord=%D0%B6%D0%B8%D0%B2%D0%BE%D1%82%D0%BD%D0%BE%D0%B5>
17. Haviland, J. B. (2006). Gesture as cultural and linguistic practice. Available at: <https://pages.ucsd.edu/~jhaviland/Publications/GESTURE%20AS%20CULTURAL%20AND%20LINGUISTIC%20PRACTICE.pdf>

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